

TRAIN4EU

Transforming ReseArch & INnovation
agendas and support in 4EU+

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ERA POLICY BRIEF

CALL: Horizon2020 - Science with and for Society (SwafS) - Other Actions 31 and 32

TOPIC: “Support for the European Universities on the Research and Innovation dimension”

PROJECT: Transforming ReseArch & INnovation agendas and support in 4eu+ (TRAIN4EU).

Website: [Research - 4EU+ Alliance \(4euplus.eu\)](https://www.4euplus.eu)

SCOPE OF THE POLICY BRIEF

TRAIN4EU is committed to develop a framework for facilitating collaboration on, and possible implementation of, future institutional transformations of selected R&I support functions within 4eu+, as well as across and beyond European University Alliances. TRAIN4EU’s feedback on progress and policy recommendations are based on mapping of common drivers of, obstacles for, and solutions to challenges and collaborations in R&I support functions emerging from cases selected for best practice assessment and innovations, framed within the Horizon2020 SwafS-32 call Transformation Modules. The cases are in the process of being analysed and potentially piloted within the project. TRAIN4EU (ERA) policy brief 1, submitted as Deliverable 7.6, must therefore be read as work in progress.

FEEDBACK ON PROGRESS

1. Please describe the **challenges** your Alliance encountered regarding cooperation between universities in the field of R&I in relation to the institutional change areas foreseen.

The 4eu+ alliance has designed its TRAIN4EU SwafS project to identify challenges and point to barriers for cooperation and potentials for overcoming them. Here, midway in our efforts, some of the challenges identified are:

In our work to pinpoint potential for *developing a common research agenda* among our six multidisciplinary universities, we find one challenge to be the substantial variation in organizational configurations, particularly for research services, along the centralization / decentralization spectrum. This implies that resources for R&I agenda setting are distributed differently, which can challenge coordination and capacity for action across the alliance. Another challenge is a growing need for trained and specialized officers able to support researchers in setting R&I agendas and pursue funding.

Turning to *strengthening R&I human capital*, where focus has been on e.g. support for early and mid-career researchers aiming to pursue careers within and outside academia, we find that across different fields, it is a challenge that the partner universities are governed by quite different national laws and institutional practices, which are not easily adapted to enable cross-university collaborations.

The 4eu+ alliance consists of strong research universities that are all acutely aware of the potential benefits as well as the experienced costs of research infrastructure. Thus, potentials for *sharing research infrastructure* has been under intense scrutiny and it has been the focus of our first open 4eu+ cross-alliance transformational knowledge sharing event. In that, we learned that across all alliances, including 4eu+, great variation in the practices of management, acquisition and funding of research infrastructures pose the main obstacles on the path towards sharing research infrastructure facilities within and across universities.

Within the areas of *linking academia with citizens and with businesses*, universities across Europe and within our alliance are in very different development stages, e.g. with respect to integrating citizens outreach or opening up for research interaction with private innovation processes. This remains both a challenge and an opportunity for learning and co-development. A similar challenge is true for *mainstreaming Open Science*, with diverse levels of development in policies, practices, infrastructure investments, staff training and competence enhancement in Open Science core aspects, FAIR and RDM.

2. Please describe how you tackled or intend to tackle these challenges.

TRAIN4EU staff from all 4eu+ universities are working on ways to tackle the often complex challenges identified within the different R&I support domains and transformation areas during the project's first 18 months. In that work they are supported by 4eu+ activities on *joint governance and collaboration*.

The creation of a legal entity (4eu+ European University Alliance e.V.) in 2021 and the consolidation of a General Secretariat enhance our ability to work towards *a common research agenda*, and take actions like the Virtual Development Office, created to pursue joint research endeavours, among other things. Joint training and peer-learning across the alliance is also expected to enhance ability for joint programming and agenda setting.

Likewise, ongoing knowledge sharing and workshops on e.g. career developments for younger researchers, may help align practices further within the area of *strengthening R&I human capital*, and further enable an informed discussion on the needs for alignment of rules and practices.

Within the area of *sharing research infrastructure*, TRAIN4EU coordinated the first cross-alliance conference and identified not only challenges, but also excellent practices for mapping, managing and sharing research infrastructure. They offer best-practice moulds, such as University of Milan's Unitech for sharing and managing a number of core infrastructures. More broadly, however, a sustainable and efficient research infrastructure facility network on European level, and a funding mechanism for HEI that creates an incentive for universities to invest in an interconnected system of research infrastructures, is called for.

Within the transformation modules of *Linking Academia-Business-Citizens*, the inter-Alliance variation in practices and experiences represent a learning opportunity, which will be exploited further in pinpointing potentials for transformative actions. A similar approach is ongoing for the area of *Mainstreaming Open Science*. Here we are in the process of further enhancing our efforts to bring forward our joint efforts in citizen science, drawing on front line examples within e.g. biodiversity research, to develop joint standards and approaches for citizen science activities.

3. Please describe the tangible progress that individual partners as well as the Alliance as a whole have made in terms of introducing changes in their entities as a result of this project.

TRAIN4EU is midway through its project lifetime, but early signs of progress include the following:

Regarding *Developing a Common Research Agenda*, our exchange of best practices and experiences among partners has resulted in internal reflections on processes and existing practices within individual universities, as well as the joint building up of an Alliance level network of research support. This latter process is developed in synergy with the 4eu+ Virtual Development Office. We also see tangible progress in terms of joint learning and cross-university inspiration on initiatives in *Strengthening R&I Human Capital*. Interesting data on practices have inspired the identification of several potential actions to pilot as transformative actions within e.g. younger researchers career development, individual performance reviews and other practices.

We have done a comprehensive mapping of research infrastructure facilities, and identified best practice in the field of *sharing research infrastructure*, with particular promise in centralised management systems. During the next phase, we aim to enable joint research across the alliance by bringing together project managers.

Within *Mainstreaming Open Science* we are seeing emerging progress on recognizing and identifying potential areas of transformative action e.g. related to citizen science practices and standards, as well as digitalization and the development of data stewardship competences.

Regarding *joint governance and collaboration within and across alliances*, we have seen significant progress in coordination and involvement, not least as revealed in the very successful 4eu+ Conference on Educational and Research Infrastructure Collaboration in European University Alliances, held on-line on June 8 2022, with more than 170 participants (please see [4eu+ website](#) for more information).

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Policy topic 1: facilitating transnational cooperation

In R&I support activities and in overall organisational initiatives focused on long term sustainability, the 4eu+ experience has revealed areas where promising solutions could be identified, as well as others where further facilitation is needed.

The Alliance jointly funded a legal entity - the 4eu+ European University Alliance e.V - to create an organisational infrastructure believed to be beneficial for enhancing joint resources, efficiency and visibility. While deeper collaboration structures are in the making, there is a need to further incentivise the investments required to implement actual institutional transformation. 4eu+ thus recommends:

- providing comprehensive, long-term funding instruments supporting cooperation among partners in all universities' missions, which would foster integrated and synergic institutional transformation while reducing management burden
- granting adequate investments. Deeper cooperation provides universities with considerable added-values, ranging from mutual exchange to, in the medium and long term, optimization of resources. Yet, it also comes with costs in terms of additional, human and financial resources needed for designing and managing joint actions. Dedicated adequate funding is fundamental to incentivise commitment and secure actual implementation of institutional change
- Enhancing alignment between EU, national and regional funding

Through such a holistic and integrated approach to funding, in the longer term, benefits may arise across most if not all universities' missions. One such mission pursued in 4eu+ is enhanced collaboration on, and management of, infrastructures supporting both research and education. Access to high level and up to date infrastructures is an important prerequisite for universities' competitiveness, and it is also a major cost driver at universities.

In TRAIN4EU, 4eu+ has studied models for improved management and sharing of research infrastructures, both within and across partner universities. By identifying best practices, piloting actions and, in parallel, developing synergies with other Alliances and institutional stakeholders, we are laying tracks for deeper transnational cooperation between diverse yet complementary institutions. In this regard, whilst it is too early for specific recommendations, the definition and features of *core facilities* are particularly being addressed with the aim of solving, within large multidisciplinary universities, the prior challenge of internal fragmentation and need for optimization.

2. Policy topic 2: strengthening careers

In TRAIN4EU, special and on-going attention is being paid to recruitment and career support for early career researchers. Different schemes and initiatives at partner universities are being analysed, including career development programmes, performance review and promotion processes, approaches to work-life balance, partners and family support services, and institutional frameworks for promoting gender

equality. With regard to a common format for a tenure-track system at EU level, the experience from universities currently employing this type of mechanisms is that they may reduce the stress for those hired in this framework. Yet tenure-track does not resolve the need to handle the career perspectives for the many PhDs and post docs not in or not entering into such positions.

There is a need for European universities to address how the wider set of potential careers paths for PhDs and post docs into the private or public sector, outside of academia, should be reflected in the skills and competences acquired in these positions, and should then be linked with assessment. 4eu+ therefore recommend that guidelines for assessments of individuals along their career path are linked to the competences they are expected to have at various career steps (not only in research), allowing for assessments to apply weights to different elements, depending on the position assessed to, with a particular focus on the PhD level in a changing landscape

With regard to the ongoing process aimed at reforming research and researchers' assessment in Europe, 4eu+ partner universities are closely monitoring and actively participating in debates and policy developments that are taking place in different settings, and strongly agree on the need for a substantial redefinition of assessment criteria, and for a more homogeneous system of assessment within ERA.

In terms of contents of the reform, 4eu+ recommends:

- the use of a multidimensional perspective in assessment, mirroring the diversity of competences expected from researchers (i.e. research, teaching, public engagement activities) and including the recognition of more transversal dimensions such leadership, management, collaboration etc.
- greater focus on quality of research and not only quantitative indicators in assessing researchers

In terms of policy process, 4eu+ recommends:

- a reform timeline considering current persisting differences across national contexts affecting the capacity of individual institutions to deploy resources and to transition to new models
- strong and early involvement of member states. Reforming assessment is a complex endeavour requiring both cultural change and profound structural transformation in regulations, with a crucial role played by national stakeholders. For member states to be among the signatories of the Agreement that is currently being drafted would represent an important sign of commitment
- development of tools (i.e. Toolkit of best practices) that can be used as possible reference in institutional change processes.
- defining support or funding opportunities aimed at sustaining efforts expected from institutions

3. Policy topic 3: digital transition

All European universities are invested in harvesting the gains from the fast developing digital transition in all their missions as well as in administrative and organisational procedures and structures. So too the 4eu+ Alliance, which has identified both general challenges and specific potentials for the digital transition. On this basis, 4eu+ recommends:

- acknowledging the distinctive role of public universities as open knowledge centres and their features in EU data provisions, as the new complex EU legislation tackling the digital transition, aimed at providing pioneering regulations, addresses private players in particular. Yet, in many cases – i.e. the Digital Services Act – the specificities of public universities are not sufficiently taken into account, with the risk of adding additional costs and hampering efficiency
- strengthening EU training in new forms of data stewardship at universities. Work in TRAIN4EU has highlighted how, even at large universities like 4eu+ members, fast-growing availability of digital infrastructures, hardware and software alike, and rules and regulations targeting e.g. data management, is outstripping the skillset of R&I support staff and researchers
- R&I infrastructure specialists in TRAIN4EU have pointed to the potential value of developing a digital platform for research infrastructure facilities across European universities. This may enable European universities to better pool expertise and resources to develop and implement

joint research and education efforts, and to pursue a new generation of digital strategies and shared interoperable IT infrastructure. In education, the Digital Education Hub is a first step

- R&I open science specialists in TRAIN4EU have further pointed to the need for strengthening open access (OA) green and diamond routes in state and institutional policies of research funding and research assessment, by defining them as mandatory ways of research outputs publications. There is an increasing dissonance between the idea and encouragement for OA publishing and the real, high costs of openness, in terms of funding issues, commercial concerns, author rights etc., which risks deteriorating science and scholarly communication

4. Policy topic 4: access to excellence

Within TRAIN4EU, the Alliance has studied how 4eu+ partner universities, who are all large comprehensive, research-intensive universities, are organised in terms of R&I activities and research support. There are significant variations in how the six universities are organised, the constraints they face, and their experience and success in attracting competitive funding, e.g. EU funding. Learning from these differences and from the collaboration established, 4eu+ recommends:

- favouring the development of sustainable pathways which call for a holistic attention to the multiple aspects of R&I activities and support functions, and for sound analyses of needs and possible types of incentives for different types of institutions
- facilitating cooperation through the support/strengthening of academic and administrative exchange programmes, which would greatly enhance exchange of knowledge and excellence, especially through on-site presence of scientists and practitioners
- supporting capacity building in terms of both training and strengthened consolidated structures dealing with R&I support. In this regard, 4eu+ supports actions such as a Research Management Initiative, aimed at developing R&I management capacity within research organisations through EU coordinated training and certifications. In an academic world marked by increasing complexity in terms of management and research support needs, the availability of trained, high profile support staff is a vital dimension and crucial organisational feature for supporting excellent research and supporting researchers' ability to perform

5. Policy topic 5: increasing global competitiveness

Significant investment in research is paying off in countries like South Korea and China and other new wealthy and up and coming economies, reducing the gap in research competitiveness between these countries, the US and Europe. In Europe, some member states have launched national excellence initiatives albeit with different timings, structures and available resources. Within TRAIN4EU, such differences have been observed while analysing the strategic priorities, organisational profiles as well as contextual features of the six universities, namely in countries where excellence initiatives were introduced and obtained funding. Based on these and other observations, 4eu+ recommends:

- planning of the European Excellence Initiative being accompanied by and building on detailed analyses of impact of existing national ones, in order to favour implementation and alignment
- continued substantial funding of curiosity-driven, basic research as this has proven its relevance also in applied settings, most recently forcefully illustrated by the COVID vaccines
- innovations in the funding of mission-oriented research supporting e.g. the Green Deal are called for, along with innovation and knowledge transfer activities enhancing uptake of new knowledge and technologies, in both public and private sectors

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